

Application of a quantitative molecular methods to characterize abundance and distribution of *Alexandrium* cysts for NOAA's HAB Forecasting

Cheryl Greengrove^{1*}, Steve Kibler², Julie Masura¹, Julie Matweyou³, Courtney Hart⁴

¹ University of Washington Tacoma, 1900 Commerce Street, Tacoma WA 98402, U.S.A.; ² NOAA Beaufort Laboratory, 101 Pivers Island Rd, Beaufort, NC 28516, U.S.A.; ³ Julie Matweyou – University of Alaska Fairbanks - Alaska Sea Grant, 118 Trident Way, Kodiak AK 99615, U.S.A.;

⁴ Courtney Hart – University of Alaska Fairbanks - Juneau Center, 17101 Point Lena Loop Road Juneau, AK 99801, U.S.A.

* corresponding author's email: cgreen@uw.edu

Abstract

The toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* overwinters as a benthic resting cyst and germinates into the water column in the spring, making cells available for filter feeding by shellfish. Previous studies have mapped winter distribution of *A. catenella* cysts in Gulf of Maine and Puget Sound sediments to provide shellfish growers/harvesters with an early warning system of potential hotspots for blooms. However, the current protocol for cyst enumeration by fluorescent microscopy is time consuming and requires highly specific training. This MERHAB project is to develop a new qPCR assay for *A. catenella* cysts for evaluation against the standard microscopy protocol to produce more rapid and accurate cyst abundance data. 2019 and 2020 sediment samples were collected in the Gulf of Maine, Puget Sound and Alaska for cyst mapping, interlaboratory comparison, and qPCR development. Interlaboratory comparisons of cyst enumeration using the standard microscopy method show no significant differences. qPCR development is underway and preliminary results are presented here.

Keywords: *Alexandrium catenella*, cysts, qPCR, forecasting, Gulf of Maine, Puget Sound, Alaska

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7036215>

Introduction

NOAA is developing *Alexandrium catenella* bloom forecast products through the harmful algal bloom (HAB) Operational Forecasting System (HABOFS) to mitigate human health risks and economic effects of shellfish closures during seasonal blooms of the toxic dinoflagellate *A. catenella* in U.S. Atlantic northeast and Pacific northwest states (<https://coastalscience.noaa.gov/research/stressor-impacts-mitigation/hab-forecasts/>). This species overwinters as a benthic resting cyst and germinates in the spring (Anderson, 2014), making saxitoxin-laden vegetative cells available for filter feeding by shellfish (Cusick and Sayler, 2013). Ingestion of shellfish containing saxitoxin by humans can result in Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) (Price *et al.*, 1991; Lefebvre *et al.*, 2016). Forecasting efforts hinge on determination of *A. catenella* cyst wintertime abundance at bloom locations.

Previous studies have mapped winter distribution of *A. catenella* cysts in Gulf of Maine (GoME; Anderson *et al.*, 2014) and Puget Sound (PS; Horner *et al.*, 2011; Greengrove *et al.*, 2015) sediments to provide shellfish growers with an early warning of potential hotspots for blooms. In addition, sediment cyst surveys in SE Alaska (Tobin *et al.*, 2017) and the Bering and Chukchi Seas (Natsuike *et al.*, 2013; Anderson *et al.*, 2021) indicate high concentrations of *A. catenella* cysts where there are limited monitoring and forecasting capabilities. The current protocol for cyst enumeration by fluorescent microscopy (Yamaguchi *et al.*, 1995) is laborious, time consuming and requires highly specific training. There is a need to streamline cyst quantification to shorten the

turnaround time in advance of the spring bloom season and make the quantification methods consistent across regions.

Fig. 1. Contour maps of *A. catenella* cyst distribution (cysts cm^{-3}) in the GoME in A) Oct 2019 and B) Oct 2020; in SE Alaska in C) summer 2019 and D) summer 2020; and in Chiniak Bay, Kodiak in E) Feb 2020, and F) Dec 2020.

Using sediment samples from the GoME, PS and AK, this project funded by NOAA's MERHAB program is to map regional *A. catenella* cyst abundances, conduct

interlaboratory comparison of the standard microscopy method for cyst enumeration to check for consistency of counts, and compare microscopy-derived abundances with those using qPCR. The same sediment samples are being used to develop and evaluate a qPCR assay for *A. catenella* cysts. This molecular work builds on prior species-specific molecular methods developed over the last two decades (Anderson *et al.*, 1999; Hosoi-Tanabe and Sako, 2005, 2006; Erdner *et al.*, 2010; Vandersea *et al.*, 2017). If successful, the new tool will provide cyst abundance data to HABOFS and other regional marine resource management systems more quickly and consistently than is currently possible with microscopy-based methods.

Material and Methods

Surface sediment samples were collected by Craib corer or Van Veen grab sampler at 54 GoME stations in Oct 2019 (Y1) and 53 stations in Oct 2020 (Y2); at 47 PS stations in Jan-Feb 2020 (Y1); at 24 stations in SE Alaska in summer 2019 (Y1) and 8 stations in 2020 (Y2); and at 12 Kodiak, Alaska stations in Feb 2020 (Y1) and Dec 2020 (Y2). Craib cores were sliced into 0-1 cm (surface) and 1-3 cm segments and retained for processing. The grab samples were sampled from the upper 2 cm of sediment with a plastic scoop. Prior to processing, the sediment samples from GoME and Alaska were split and subsamples were sent to University of Washington Tacoma (UWT) for duplicate counting as part of the interlaboratory comparison. Samples from PS and Alaska were split and subsamples were sent to the NOAA Beaufort Lab for qPCR development. The 0-1 cm GoME samples and all samples from PS and Alaska were processed and enumerated

at each investigator's lab using the standard microscopy method (Yamaguchi *et al.*, 1995). Cyst abundances were mapped using ArcGIS and microscopy-based cyst enumeration results were compared among labs using a t-test (normal data) or Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test (non-normal).

Sediment samples for cyst counting and qPCR were homogenized, and a 5 cm³ subsample collected for processing. Subsamples were sonicated and sieved to isolate the 20-100 μm cyst fraction after (Anderson *et al.*, 2005). The cyst fraction was concentrated onto a 47 mm, 8 μm Nucleopore™ polycarbonate filter and DNA was extracted using the Nucleospin Soil DNA extraction Kit (Takara Bio U.S.A., Inc., San Jose, CA) with lysis buffer SL1 after the manufacturer's protocol. A FastPrep-24 Classic™ bead beater (MP Biomedicals, Santa Ana, CA) was used to disrupt cysts in each sample at a speed of 6.0 m s⁻¹ for 1 min. The DNA was eluted in 50 μL and qPCR amplified with a BIO RAD CFX Connect™ real time system (BIO RAD, Hercules, CA) (Vandersea *et al.*, 2017). The qPCR reaction mix contained SYBR green QuantiNova Probe PCR Master Mix (Qiagen, Germantown, MD) and 1 μL of each DNA extract using a quantification cycle (Cq) after Bustin *et al.* (2009). A melting curve analysis was performed following thermal cycling to check the specificity of the PCR reactions.

Cyst-based qPCR standard curves were constructed using microscopy-based counts. A cyst concentrate was first created by processing multiple aliquots of sediment with the method above, and using density gradient centrifugation (Richlen *et al.*, 2016) to concentrate the cysts and remove contaminating particulates. Aliquots of the

cyst concentrate (1-1,000 cysts) were then extracted for qPCR with identical aliquots for cyst counts. Standard curves were constructed by plotting the Cq values vs log transformed cyst concentrations, and linear regression analysis was used to calculate the slope.

Fig. 2. A) *Alexandrium catenella* cyst distribution (cysts cm^{-3}) in PS during Feb 2020. B) Draft qPCR standard curve for cysts.

Results and Discussion

Cyst distribution maps for GoME, PS, SE Alaska and Kodiak are shown in figures 1-4. Note that no Y2 data were collected for PS due to sampling constraints associated with the COVID pandemic. Y1 cyst abundances in the GoME were highest offshore between Casco Bay and Penobscot Bay and NE of Grand Manan Island near the mouth of the Bay of Fundy (Anderson *et al.*, 2014). Y2 cyst abundances were lower overall with lower abundances. In PS during Y1, cyst abundances were generally lower than prior studies (Horner *et al.*, 2011; Greengrove *et al.*, 2015), but with high cyst abundances in Quartermaster Harbor, Bellingham Bay, and bays in the western Main Basin of PS. One area of increased cyst abundance is Penn Cove, which has historically been a site with PSP toxin occurrences (Trainer *et al.*, 2003). In SE Alaska, high Y1 cyst abundances were found on the west coasts of Prince of Wales Is. (near Craig) and Gravina Is. (near Ketchikan); and between Annette and Duke Is. in Sealed Passage. Only the Ketchikan area was sampled in Y2 with less cysts overall compared to the prior year. Kodiak had high cyst abundances throughout Chiniak Bay in both years and Womens Bay had even higher cyst abundances in Y2 than Y1. Overall, cysts were present in all three areas (GoME, PS and coastal Alaska), but Alaska cyst abundances were the highest of all three regions (2019 and 2020).

Cyst enumeration results from the NOAA Beaufort Lab and the UWTLab were compared for not found to be statistically different ($p = 0.906$). Also, no statistical differences were found when comparing University Alaska Fairbanks (UAF) - Juneau Lab and the UWT

Lab cyst counts for both years ($p = 0.057$). A comparison between the UAF – Kodiak Lab and UWT is still pending. The results thus far indicate that with proper cross-lab training, *A. catenella* cyst enumeration can be consistent.

Method development of the cyst qPCR assay is proceeding. The draft qPCR standard curve (Fig. 5) indicates the qPCR cyst assay is linear over six orders of magnitude ($y = 26.2 - 3.2x$, $r^2 = 0.94$, $p < 0.05$), and can be used to estimate cyst abundance in the GoME, PS and Alaska. This assay is an improvement over a previous qPCR assay by Erdner *et al.* (2010) because we use a cyst-based standard curve (instead of an amplicon) with a greater dynamic range (six orders of magnitude). Further testing is underway before assay validation with microscopy- and qPCR-derived abundances over multiple seasons. Pending favorable validation results, the assay will be used to map cyst distribution, and will be integrated into HABOFS forecast results.

Acknowledgements. This project is funded by NOAA National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science (NCCOS) MERHAB grant number NA19NOS4780188.

References

Anderson, D.M., Fachon, E., Pickart, R.S., Lin, P., *et al.* (2021). PNAS 118, e2107387118.

Anderson, D.M., Keafer, B.A., Kleindinst, J.L., McGillicuddy Jr., *et al.* (2014). Deep-Sea Res. II 103, 6-26.

Anderson, D.M., Kulis, D.M., Keafer, B.A., Berdalet, E. (1999). J. Phycol. 35, 870-883.

Anderson, D.M., Stock, C.A. Keafer, B.A.,

Bronzino, A., *et al.* (2005). Deep Sea Res. II 52, 2522-2542.

Bustin S.A., Benes V., Garson J.A., Hellemans J., *et al.* 2009. Clin. Chem. 55, 611-622.

Cusick, K.D. and Sayler, G.S. (2013). Mar. Drugs 11, 991-1018.

Erdner, D.L., Percy, L., Keafer, B., Lewis, J., Anderson, D.M. (2010). Deep-Sea Res. II 57, 279-287.

Greengrove, C.L., Masura, J.E., Moore, S.K., Bill, B.D., *et al.* (2015). In: MacKenzie, A.L. (Ed.) Proc. 16th ICHA. Wellington, New Zealand. 163-166.

Horner, R.A., Greengrove, C.L., Davies-Vollum, K.S., Gawel, J.E., Postel, J.R., Cox, A. (2011). Harmful Algae 11, 96-105.

Hosoi-Tanabe, S. and Sako, Y. (2005). Harmful Algae 4, 319-328.

Hosoi-Tanabe, S. and Sako, Y. (2006). Fish. Sci. 72, 77-82.

Lefebvre, K.A., Quakenbush, L., Frame, E., Burek Huntington, K., *et al.* (2016). Harmful Algae 55, 13-24.

Natsuike, M., Nagai, S., Matsuno, K., Saito, R., Tsukazaki, C., *et al.*, (2013). Harmful Algae 27, 52-59.

Price, D.W., Kizer, K.W., Hansgen, K.H. (1991). J. Shellfish Res. 10, 119-145.

Richlen, M.L., Zielinski, O., Holinde, L., Tillman, U., *et al.*, (2016). Mar. Ecol. Progr. Ser. 547, 33-46.

Tobin, E., Eckert, G., Whitehead, C., Sullivan, K. (2017). Alaska Marine Science Symposium, Anchorage, Alaska.

Trainer, V.L., Eberhart, B.-T.L., Wekell, J.C., Adams, N.G., *et al.*, (2003). J. Shellfish Res. 22, 213-223.

Vandersea M.W., Kibler S.R., Van Sant S.B., Tester P.A., *et al.* (2017). Phycologia 56, 303-320.

Yamaguchi, M., Itakura, S., Imai, I., Ishida, Y. (1995). Phycologia 34, 207-214.

